

STRATEGIES FOR DEVELOPING THE EFFECTIVE MANAGEMENT SYSTEM OF SPORTS FEDERATIONS AND ASSOCIATIONS

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Abstract. *In addition to being a member of prestigious international organizations, the Republic of Uzbekistan has become an equal member of a number of international organizations in order to develop the field of physical education and sports based on the principles of foreign policy, as well as state organizations. The broad development of the international sports and Olympic movement, the holding of various sports competitions on the continents, the continental games, the traditional organization of the world championships and the Olympic Games are demanding in the development of sports in each country in the era of globalization.*

Keywords: *sportsmen, tournament, Olympic glory, political and racial discrimination, International Universiade, Mass and Health Physical Education.*

As an independent country, Uzbekistan established the National Olympic Committee in order to become a member of international sports communities. This was done at the first constituent assembly on January 21, 1992. Based on the charter of the IOC and relying on the best practices of the world sports movement, the IOC statute (charter) was developed and adopted. The contribution of the first President of the Republic of Uzbekistan in the relations of the Republic with international sports organizations is very great. On February 6, 1996, I.A. Karimov was awarded the Olympic gold medal by the International Olympic Committee after two visits of the President of the International Olympic Committee H.A. Samaranch to our country (1994-1995), leaders of the Arab countries, the President of the Asian Games Council and UNESCO. The arrival of officials to Uzbekistan was an important event. As a result, in August 1996, the "Olympic Glory" museum was opened in Tashkent. The sports history of our country, the Olympic movement, and the achievements of athletes were expressed in it.

Currently, there is a flag, emblem and slogan of the Olympic movement. The full recognition of the National Olympic Committee of Uzbekistan by the International Olympic Committee in 1993 was a great event in the spiritual life of our country. The National Olympic Committee of Uzbekistan includes Olympic clubs, republican sports federations, Olympic Academies and a number of public and non-governmental organizations in the field of physical education and sports. In his speech at the opening ceremony of the Museum of Olympic Fame on September 1, 1996, the first President of the Republic of Uzbekistan said, "With luck, the flame of the Olympic Games will be lit in Tashkent. The sportsmen of Uzbekistan are still making the name of our country famous by surprising the opponents and spectators in many tournaments".

As we know from history, it is an objective fact that national sports organizations appear as a component of the social life of the state, as representatives of the ruling political and ideological views in it. In this sense, Uzbekistan's entry into the international arenas in the field of sports with the honour of its independence, and the cooperation relations being conducted in the field of sports show that it is a necessary condition for the adherence and development of the

international sports movement to the existing principles generally accepted at the current stage. It can be seen in the following that our Constitution, which conforms to the norms of international law, and the international principles that form the basis of the adopted Laws and Decisions are in full compliance with the following:

- comprehensive development of sports;
- fight against political and racial discrimination in sports;
- recognition of the sovereignty and equality of national sports organizations;
- non-interference in the activities of national sports organizations;
- the organization and activities of international sports organizations based on a democratic basis;
- participation in the struggle to achieve peace and mutual understanding in the world, etc.

In general, both international and national sports organizations study the activities of the most important institutions of international law and conduct their activities based on the generally recognized norms of international law, in order to educate them on the level of the athletes of Uzbekistan when they take them to the world arena. Sports organizations of the Republic of Uzbekistan participate in the activities of almost all international sports organizations. International sports organizations related to sports that are not popular in our country are excluded. In the international sports movement, the emergence of organizational structures with specific goals and tasks and having work experience has become a natural phenomenon. The main ones are: International Olympic Movement, International Sports Movements in Specific Sports, International Sports Movements in Professional Sports, International Sports Movements of Youth and Students, International Universiade, Mass and Health Physical Education and Sports Movements, which are organized by international cooperation in the field of physical education and sports.

International sports organizations that implement the international sports movement occupy the most important place in the organization and holding of competitions. It is no exaggeration to say that the sum of international organizations is the organizational and legal basis of international sports relations. First of all, international organizations can be classified according to the subject of activity, i.e. specific areas of international relations related to a certain organization. In particular, international sports organizations, like other international organizations, are distinguished by the subject of their activity, more precisely, international sports relations. International sports organizations that organize and hold international competitions are recognized as international institutions that have certain functional tasks based on their founding documents and are recognized as subjects of international law and have the status of an international organization. The scope of legal subjectivity of different international organizations is also different, and it expresses the will of the subjects who founded them. Their nature is defined in the relevant founding documents on the regulation of issues of membership, status, powers, relations with states and other international organizations. There are international organizations with general competence dealing with physical education and sports issues, these organizations combine the qualities of general international law and international sports law. They primarily act as coordinators of international cooperation in the field of sports activities. The most important place in the field of international sports cooperation is occupied by the United Nations and its specialized organizations.

Currently, the UN is the centre of many forms of cooperation in the field of sports. There are also network organizations of the UN specialized in the development of physical education and sports activities. Among them, the United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization and the World Health Organization can be recognized.

International organizations (or international sports organizations) with special competence. Obviously, international organizations with common competence alone are not enough to ensure mutual relations emerging in the field of sports. This goal is also served by specialized international sports organizations whose activities are directly focused on sports. International sports organizations are global and regional non-governmental international organizations in physical culture, physical education and sports.

International non-governmental organizations are national public organizations of different countries, unions, groups and associations of individuals, and are recognized as organizations aiming to promote international cooperation in the political, economic, cultural, scientific and technical and other spheres of human activity. Such organizations are not created on the basis of an intergovernmental agreement and do not intend to obtain commercial benefits.

Members of international sports organizations can be national, and in some cases, international sports organizations, as well as individual institutions and individuals related to activities in the field of physical culture, physical education and sports. The international sports movement is organized and operated by a large number of international sports organizations. Such organizations can be divided into the following main groups:

1. General international sports organizations.
2. International sports organizations for specific sports.
3. International sports organizations in the fields of training and activity.
4. International sports organizations of certain relevance.

International sports organizations of a general nature are not limited to a specific field of physical education and sports. Such organizations include the International Olympic Committee, the International Council for Sports Science, Physical Education and Sports, the General Association of National Olympic Committees, the General Association of International Sports Federations, the International Federation of Physical Education, the International Olympic Academy.

The core of the modern international sports system is the International Olympic Committee, which was founded on June 23, 1894 at the I Olympic Congress in Paris by Perdie Coubertin. From a legal point of view, the International Olympic Committee is a non-profit international non-governmental organization established in the form of an association with the status of a legal entity recognized by the Swiss Federal Council. According to Article 60 of the Swiss Civil Code, the International Olympic Committee was established as a Swiss private law association. According to the International Olympic Charter, the main task of the International Olympic Committee is to lead the Olympic movement. According to the charter, the International Olympic Committee, as the supreme authority of the Olympic movement, coordinates and encourages the development of sports and sports competitions, as well as cooperation with public associations and competent state bodies in the field of sports, in order to serve the people of sport, ensures the continuous holding of the Olympic Games, leads the fight against doping, serves to ensure the right of everyone to engage in sports, strengthens friendship between peoples and performs other similar tasks.

Decisions of the International Olympic Committee adopted on the basis of the provisions of the Olympic Charter are final decisions. All disputes arising from their application can be resolved only by the Executive Committee of the International Olympic Committee and in some cases by the International Court of Arbitration for Sport.

The International Council for Sports Science, Physical Education and Sport (ICSSPE) was founded in Paris in 1958. It is one of the most prestigious organizations dealing with the development and dissemination of sports science, physical education and sports knowledge and their practical application. The Council defines the following as its goals: Coordination of activities of international state and non-state organizations, as well as national organizations in the field of sports science, physical education and sports; Development of the scientific and methodological foundations of physical education and sports in the world.

Currently, ICSSPE has more than 200 members from 60 countries representing international and national sports organizations, scientific and educational institutions, as well as individuals. ICSSPE cooperates with the International Olympic Committee, UNESCO and the International Health Organization. The main activity of this organization is to support and promote the further activation and development of theoretical research in the field of physical education and sports.

The General Association of National Olympic Committees (NAOC) was founded in Mexico City in 1968, and its headquarters are located in Rome. The General Association unites more than 200 National Olympic Committees. MOQBA meetings are held every two years. The official languages are English, Spanish, Russian and French. The goal of the organization is to further develop the Olympic movement, to submit proposals to the International Olympic Committee for the improvement of the Olympic movement, to cooperate closely with the International Olympic Committee in other areas of activity. At a time when efforts are being made to take over the country, special attention is being paid to the health of the youth, who are the nation's gene pool and the future of the country. As Uzbekistan cooperates in every way with international countries as a subject with equal rights, the field of physical education and sports is no exception.

The most influential organization in the field of marketing is the American Marketing Association. This organization issues an updated marketing plan every 3 years. Because it's so volatile, it gets updated frequently. What was said about marketing 20 years ago may not be true today.

Without scientific terms, in a simple way, marketing is not only selling a product, service, but also always communicating with people who use the service and goods. Because it's bad marketing to say that once you've made a sale, you don't want to do anything else with it. Whether you are a producer or not, you are always in communication with the consumer.

Nowadays, it is possible to communicate with consumers through social networks or other methods. Why is this necessary? In developing the next products, the opinion of the person who is currently using the product is important to know how it affects the users.

In marketing, there are many examples from western countries - America, European countries; in the east – from Japan. Marketing in these countries has reached such a level that it has become a separate field of science. It's just dawning on us. There are aspects of marketing that are closer to sociology. We use many rules together. Because in marketing research, we study a

person's thoughts before buying products and services, how a product evokes feelings in people, why they buy this service or product, what changes it has caused in their life and work.

In my scientific research, I looked for answers to the questions of why and for what purpose people use smartphones, and I studied this on the example of different countries. Why, it varies with different societies and people? For example, in the West, people buy a smartphone if it helps them to improve their productivity in their daily work or life. In Asia, it's a bit different, people around influence customers. In most cases, he takes the newest model, but its technical aspects and capabilities are not taken into account, he just carries it. In society, the status of using a smartphone is high, there is a concept that if people use a smartphone, then I should use it too.

But as I said above, marketing is very complex and broad, not only selling products and services, the fact that even political parties use marketing services shows how wide the scope of marketing research and marketing field is.

As for Uzbekistan, I haven't made any big observations after being in the country for a long time. There is still no complete and satisfactory understanding of marketing in Uzbekistan. Marketing means only advertising, selling a certain product or service.

It can be seen that marketing is behind compared to other countries. Marketing research is a new field for Uzbekistan.

In small firms and companies, the duties of a marketer are mainly performed by the head of the firm, who although does not have a specialist diploma in this field, does these things for his company. And in large corporations, marketing departments do these things, 200-300 people conduct marketing research, as I said above.

In addition, some companies purchase marketing services. For example, in South Korea, Samsung used to buy professional marketing services from companies, no matter how large and diversified the company was. Because there, too, marketing is considered a science.

At the same time, the analysis shows that the levers of influence of the sports services industry on the economic development of the country and its regions as a whole have not been studied in depth enough, modelling of interactions and dependencies in the provision of sports marketing from the point of view of competitiveness in the service sector issues are not sufficiently described, the sports marketing mechanism for the development of sports marketing, the training of athletes and the development of the population's participation in sports in general is not sufficiently formed. The research work is dedicated to highlighting and researching current issues to increase the effectiveness of marketing services in physical education and sports educational institutions.

At the same time, the development of the marketing system in the organization of the sports services market in the conditions of Uzbekistan has been little studied. In the context of the development of relations between two countries, the high socio-economic nature and importance of the consumer market, in particular, sports services, and the fact that many aspects of the marketing system are not scientifically substantiated at a staged level, made it necessary to choose this topic as a research work.

It is important to improve the role of sports management while increasing the role of sports management in our country. The implementation of the development model of sports management in the field of physical education and sports in Uzbekistan is the basis for comprehensively solving the existing problems and current issues in the field. Its target core is to create an innovative model aimed at ensuring the financial independence of sports organizations related to the development

of mass sports in the territory of our country and creating appropriate conditions for their prospective development, based on the formation of a methodology for evaluating the development of physical education and sports. "Strategic sports management for physical education and sports development" is aimed at determining the strategies of corporate target sports management, developing an innovative methodology for determining the demand for young talented athletes, creating an economic model for meeting the demand for sports services and ensuring competitiveness in world markets concept.

The proposed decision-making model for the systematic improvement of sports management in sports organizations and enterprises and the establishment of cooperative relations is of great importance in management based on a situational approach. Management is used as an integrated system in all organizations, enterprises and institutions in the field of physical education and sports. The proposed strategic management model plays an important role in this. This model covers all aspects of economic entities in the field of physical education and sports in the direction of corporate strategy, business strategy and functional strategy. Modernization and diversification of real sector networks using advanced technologies, and for this, expansion of international integration relations between science and production, effective use of foreign investments and organization of a management system are of great importance. It involves the formation of modern features to change the selected object in accordance with the students of the new modern era and performs the following tasks.

Спорт соҳасини стратегик бошқаришда модернизация жараёнини амалга ошириш учун лозим бўлган вазифалар			
№	Ҳуқуқий базани шакллантириб бориш	Спорт хизмати самарадорлигини ошириб бориш	Моддий-техник базани мустақкамлаб бориш
1	ҳуқуқий-меъёрий базасини тақомиллаштириш, масъулиятни ошириш	Янги авлоднинг эҳтиёжлари, қизиқшлари, имкониятларини ўрганиб бориш	Моддий таъминотнинг янги манбааларини аниқлаш
2	Жисмоний тарбия ва спорт билан шуғулланиш ҳуқуқини таъминланиши	Спорт хизматларини кенгайтириш	Замонавий техник воситалар билан ва замонавий алоқа билан таъминтлаш
3	Шаффофликни таъминлаш	Спорт хизмати самарадорлигини кафолатловчи ёндашувларни жорий этиш	Спорт билан шуғулланувчиларни мотивларини кучайтириш

There are four main types of strategy:

1. Concentrated growth strategy - strategy of strengthening market positions, market development strategy, product development strategy.
2. Integrated growth strategies - reverse vertical integration strategy, forward vertical integration strategy.
3. Diversification growth strategy - centralized diversification strategy, horizontal diversification strategy.
4. Reduction strategy - loss strategy, reduction strategy, cost reduction strategy.

Once you've decided to diversify, you have several options to choose from. There is a different typology of strategies, that is, there are six corresponding strategies:

1. Strategies of Implementation of New Sports Industry. Creating new companies and joint ventures.
2. The strategy depending on diversification.
3. Unrelated diversification strategy.
4. Withdrawal and Termination Strategies.
5. Renewal, downsizing and restructuring strategies of the company. Multinational diversification strategies.

The first three points outline diversification methods and recent strategic directions that will improve the performance of companies that are already diversified.

1. New Business Entry Strategies.

New business introduction can take one of three forms:

- reception;
- creation of a new company;
- joint venture.

Acquiring an existing business is the most popular means of diversification into another industry, and its advantage is that it is the fastest way to reach a target market. This approach helps a diversifying company overcome such barriers by acquiring technological expertise, building relationships with suppliers, and many other needs.

In order to attract competition in the desired market, diversification can be achieved by creating a new company "downwind" of the entire corporation. The new organization is not only about removing barriers to entry, but also about attracting investments in new production facilities, organizing supplies, hiring and training employees, organizing distribution channels, expanding the consumer base, etc.

Joint ventures are one of the most convenient ways to acquire new businesses, in at least three ways. First, joint ventures are a good organizational form for conducting such activities that are uneconomical or highly demanding for a single company. Second, joint ventures are important when they combine the resources of two or more independent companies and create an organization that combines their expertise with everything needed to become a strong competitor. In this case, each of the partners brings knowledge and resources that the others do not have and are necessary for success. Third, joint ventures with foreign partners are sometimes the only or best way to overcome import quotas, tariffs, national and political interests, and cultural barriers.

There are two options when choosing an industry to diversify into: companies related to the core business and diversification into non-core companies. Strategic diversification means introducing a business to a particular "strategic game". There is a strategic fit if the production cycles of different enterprises are sufficiently related.

Diversified companies that take advantage of the interdependence of production cycles and strategic alignment achieve greater overall productivity than the companies would achieve if they operated independently of each other. Strategic compatibility in a diversified portfolio of activities, together with the energy and skills of corporate management, allows to obtain the type of diversification ($2 + 2 = 5$) that forms the basis of competitiveness in order to create mutual interest. When the benefits of strategic fit are substantial, competitive advantage arises from this type of diversification, and this type of product satisfies the test conditions for improvement in creating

market value for a larger share. Diversification is important. This allows to preserve the unity of the business, to gain a competitive advantage from the transfer of experience and skills, and to diversify the investor's wider business risk. Diversification of such business, technology, manufacturing facilities, production services, and distribution channels that can be used together can reduce costs arising from economies of scale. The effect of scale is always realized where the work of two or more enterprises with centralized management is less expensive than if these enterprises operate independently. It arises from the joint work of a group of enterprises or production branches, from the realization of opportunities to collect funds, share resources or production capacity in the relevant production periods of the business, as well as share a generally recognized brand. The greater is the quantitative impact of a company's diversification into a particular business, the greater is the opportunity to create a competitive edge based on lower costs.

Currently, the processes of modernization, diversification, decentralization of the economy, liberalization of foreign trade and development of foreign economic relations are actively taking place. Therefore, it is necessary to develop the main directions of modernization of physical education and sports activities.

Day by day, the number of independent thinking leaders who want to take their place in the target market, increase the activity and living standards of the employees in the organization is increasing. The main goal of any organization is to provide high-quality service at low cost and achieve maximum profit. The establishment of new structures places higher demands on the employees working in them and their professional training. In order to organize service delivery, the leader must be able to clearly see the goal and choose the right way to achieve it.

At the current stage of economic development, effective management decisions on the organization of physical education and sports activities require the joint efforts of sports managers, trainers, technologists and others.

At the current stage of economic development, making effective management decisions on the organization of physical education and sports activities requires the joint action of specialists in various fields: sports managers, trainers, technologists, and others.

In this regard, the role of event management in the development of the effective management system of the service market in the field of physical education and sports is extremely important. It is necessary to improve the planning of sports events based on the requirements of event management, the management of special social projects in the field of sports services. Event management is focused on the development of services, products, company, events and brand. Event management includes the organization and management of sports events, the search for necessary financial resources and information, the organization of sports events, the provision of basic and additional services, the matching of athletes and trainers with service personnel and performs such tasks as achieving coordination of mutual activities, organizing the flow of spectators and ensuring their safety. In order to develop such a management system, it is necessary to determine the main factors of providing convenient services to the population.

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